

*Minimum Effective Dose of Exogenous Melatonin Pretreatment in Ameliorating Nephrotoxicity Caused by Ampicillin Sodium in Wild Tropical Rodent, Indian Palm Squirrel, *F. pennanti*.*

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Introduction:

Melatonin, the main product of the pineal gland, participates in many physiological functions due to its efficacy as a free radical scavenger and indirect antioxidant (Reiter et al., 2001; Tan et al., 2002; Allegra et al., 2003; Reiter, 2003). Because of its small size and lipophilicity, melatonin crosses biological membranes easily, thus, reaching all compartments of the cell. Melatonin has also been shown to be an efficient protector of DNA (Lopez-Burillo et al., 2003), protein and lipids in cellular membrane (Melchiorri et al., 1995; Cuzzocrea and Reiter, 2001) as well as antagonist of a number of endogenous and exogenous free radicals attach or during cellular processes (Zang et al., 1998). It readily scavenges hydroxyl radicals (OH) formed by the ultraviolet photolysis of H₂O₂ (Tan et al., 1993) as well as by other means (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2000; Bromme et al., 2000; Stasica et al., 2000). The in vivo antioxidative effect was initially shown by its ability to significantly decrease free radical-induced alterations of hepatocyte DNA in the rats exposed to safrole (Tan et al., 1993b). The antioxidative properties of melatonin have been frequently confirmed in recent years (Reiter, 1998). Melatonin also reportedly scavenges the peroxy radical (Pieri et al., 1994) although this finding has not always been documented in subsequent studies. In addition to its function as a direct scavenger, melatonin also stimulates the activities of several antioxidative enzymes (Antolin et al., 1996; Kotler et al., 1998). When melatonin scavenges the OH, the metabolite produced is N1-acetyl-N2-formyl-5-methoxykynuramine (Hardeland et al., 1993; Poeggeler et al., 1994) and/or cyclic 3-hydroxymelatonin (Tan et al., 1998, 1999). The antioxidant properties of melatonin have been documented in a wide variety of studies (Tan et al., 1993b; Abe et al., 1994; Vijaylakshmi et al., 1995).

From the previous studies and many case reports it is very much clear that ampicillin at higher doses in acute cases produces nephrotoxicity by altering the basic functions of Glomerulous and overall kidney. In our study we have seen that the toxicity is also seen at dose (40mg/kg body wt.) which is even lower than the dose used for clinical trials. The renal tissue

being main source of the excreted urinary enzymes and the evaluation of these enzymes level is known to be a good and sensitive noninvasive method to measure the tubular cells integrity (Jung and Burchardt 1987; Price, 1982).

The physiological dose of melatonin pretreatment in our study of rats (250 µg/Kg body wt.) and others has proven to be a nephroprotective agent against oxidative stress producing agents and antibiotics. So we have selected three doses of melatonin excluding the physiological dose for our study. The aim of the present study was to investigate the highest protective potential dose of melatonin in reducing the oxidative stress by biochemical and morphological changes in ampicillin sodium induced nephrotoxicity in a wild tropical rodent Indian palm squirrel *F. pennanti*.

Experimental setup:

Thirty five (35) adult male squirrels (weighing 100-120g each) were used in this study. The squirrels were collected in the month of February from the vicinity of the Varanasi (Lat. 25°18'N; Long. 83°01'E) and acclimatized for one week in a room fully exposed to ambient environmental conditions (Light 12.50 hr; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The animals were housed in wire net cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had an access to food consisting of soaked gram seeds (*Cicer arietinum*) and water ad libitum. Later, the Squirrels were divided into five groups of 7 animals each,

Group I: Control

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition (Control) as mentioned above without any treatment.

Group II: Ampicillin treated

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am as mentioned in material & method.

Group III: Ampicillin treated + Melatonin 100µg/Kg body wt. (Amp+100)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am and Melatonin (100µg/kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Group IV: Ampicillin treated + Melatonin 500µg/Kg body wt. (Amp+500)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am and Melatonin (500µg/kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Group V: Ampicillin treated + Melatonin 1000µg/Kg body wt. (Amp+1000)

Seven adult male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am and Melatonin (1000µg/kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Sample collection:

The treatment was given for total seven days (i.e. total seven melatonin injection and seven plus seven melatonin followed by ampicillin injection). On eighth day i.e. after 24 hours of last treatment rats were sacrificed by decapitation after complete ether anesthesia. The

urinary bladder was surgically extruded and emptied in a sterile tube by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histology. The experiment and handling of animals were performed in accordance with institutional practice and within the framework of revised Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act of 2003 and 2007 of Govt. of India on animal welfare.

Parameters Assayed:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day that is after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. The bladder was surgically extruded and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, thus urine was collected, and its volume was measured and biochemical parameters ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea were estimated. After removal of both kidneys through a midline abdominal incision, the right and left kidneys were processed. The kidneys were stripped from their capsule, weighed, and slit by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla) and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were separated under a dissecting microscope. The accuracy of the dissection was verified by light microscopy. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histology.

Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the estimation of total protein, Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), Lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) and Total antioxidant capacity (TAS%). Trunk Blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes and blood/plasma was taken for biochemical estimations that are BUN, ACP, ALP and Creatinine.

Histology:

After fixation in Bouin's fluid for 22 hours, kidney was paraffin embedded and cut into 6- μ m sections. Deparaffinized sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin. Kidney morphology was observed under microscope (Leica MPV-3, Germany). The morphometric analysis of capsular space and cellular integrity (PCT, DCT & glomerulus) of kidney cortical region were done in 20 serial sections randomly selected from each animal with the help of filar ocular micrometer (Webcon Pvt. Ltd. India)

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations.

Results:

Fig. 1

Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) on Acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in (C) blood, (D) urine of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

Fig. 2

Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) on (A) blood urea nitrogen (B) urine urea and creatinine in (C) blood (D) urine of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

Fig. 3

(A) Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) on the TBARS level of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

(B) Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) on the total kidney cortical protein weight of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

(C) Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

(D) Effect of different doses of Melatonin pretreatment (100µg, 500µg and 1000µg/Kg body wt) the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (Amp), Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100, Amp+500, Amp+1000) groups.

Plate 1
Plate 1

Histomicrograph of squirrel kidney cortical region showing Glomerulus (G), increased capsular space (\rightarrow), affected brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henle and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

- A- Control (Control)
- B- Ampicillin treated (Amp)
- C- Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+100 μ g)
- D- Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+500 μ g)
- E- Ampicillin + Melatonin pretreated (Amp+1000 μ g)

The exogenous treatment of melatonin (100, 500 and 1000 μ g/Kg body wt.) to the squirrels treated with ampicillin decreased ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea in a dose dependent manner in both serum and urine significantly ($p < 0.01$) when compared to controls from ampicillin treated groups (Fig. 1 & 2). The increased biochemical parameters due to ampicillin treatment were restored to the controls best by (500 μ g/kg body wt.) while no significant decrease was noted by higher doses of melatonin pretreatment. In kidney, cortical tissues homogenates Only TBARS level decreased significantly ($p < 0.01$) while SOD activity and TAS% had no effect (Fig. 3). The dose (500 μ g/kg body wt.) ameliorated the toxic effects of ampicillin (40mg/kg body wt.) to the controls as seen from the biochemical parameters of blood and urine and from cortical tissue homogenates. The biochemical parameters are confirmed by the histological observation.

Histological observation showed significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in capsular space in Ampicillin treated groups while there was no significant change observed in the groups pretreated with 500 μ g melatonin and control (Plate1 & Table 1).

Discussion:

As it is well known that creatinine is an important measure of renal function. A significant decline in creatinine levels of blood and urine in the present study after ampicillin treatment suggests impairment of glomerular functions and cellular alteration as inferred by histological observations of Ampicillin treatment. Altered ACP and ALP activities in the Ampicillin treated groups support the research findings due to other antibiotics gentamycin, ochratoxin etc. The resulting inhibition in the enzyme activities might be due to alterations in lysosomal activity and membrane permeability, respectively. The formation of lipid free radicals and lipid peroxide is considered an important feature of cell injury. Abundance of free radicals could lead to uncontrolled chain reactions and lipid peroxidation. The enhanced levels of lipid peroxidation (TBARS) in the present study reveal Ampicillin induced lipid peroxidation in the kidney via free radicals. Melatonin is a proven antioxidant an added feature that possibly increases the efficiency of melatonin in reducing oxidative stress is that metabolites that are produced during the scavenging action of melatonin also seem to be efficient scavengers (Reiter et al., 1997). For this reason, instead of scavenging a single radical, melatonin via an antioxidant cascade may neutralize a number of toxic reactants. (Reiter et al., 2001, 2003)

Melatonin treatment along with Ampicillin reduced the nephrotoxic pattern in kidney, since all the above-mentioned biochemical parameters were altered after Ampicillin treatment when compared to the controls, confirming the antioxidative properties of melatonin. Thus the results obtained from the present study suggest a protective action of melatonin against Ampicillin sodium caused nephrotoxicity due to increased free radical load which is a part of antibiotic action mechanism. In conclusion, the present data document that ampicillin sodium caused increase in the free radical load causing structural and biochemical alterations which is best ameliorated by a dose double the physiological dose (500µg/kg body weight) in our study of ampicillin treated squirrels. Melatonin has the ability to protect kidneys from the damaging effects of ampicillin treatment through inhibition of lipid peroxidation and stimulation of endogenous antioxidative defense system.

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